

PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS.

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Annotation: In this thesis, opinions and reflections are made on the pedagogical factors of the development of professional competence of students. The development of professional competence of students involves the acquisition of knowledge, skills and relationships necessary to become a competent and responsible specialist in their field. Teachers must clearly set learning goals for their courses and communicate them to their students. Academic goals must meet the professional standards of the field and help students develop relevant competencies.

Key words: Students, ethnicity, competence, development, pedagogical factors, methods, professional skills, relationships.

Actual assessments, such as Case Studies, simulations, or project-based assignments, are more closely related to actual work situations than traditional exams. These assessments help students develop professional skills and knowledge in Real-world conditions. Regular, timely, and constructive feedback is important to help students develop their professional skills. Feedback should be specific to educational goals and aimed at identifying areas of improvement.

Professional competence requires not only knowledge and skills. Students must also develop the ability to analyze complex problems, think critically, and develop evidence-based solutions. Teachers can promote critical thinking and problem solving by giving students the opportunity to engage in challenging questions and scenarios.

Effective communication is an important skill for professionals in all areas. Teachers can help students develop communication skills, including oral and written communication, and encourage them to engage in conversation and discussion. Moral and social responsibility is an important component of professional competence. Teachers can provide opportunities for students to reflect.

The development of professional competence in students is influenced by various pedagogical factors that play a significant role in their educational journey. Here are some key factors that contribute to the development of professional competence:

- **Curriculum Design:** The design of the curriculum plays a crucial role in developing professional competence. A well-structured curriculum should include a balance between theoretical knowledge and practical application, providing students with opportunities to gain hands-on experience in their field of study.
- **Active Learning:** Active learning methods, such as problem-solving activities, case studies, group discussions, and project-based learning, promote the development of critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and practical application of knowledge. These approaches encourage students to engage actively in the learning process and develop their professional competence through real-life scenarios.
- **Competency-Based Education:** A competency-based approach focuses on defining specific learning outcomes and assessing students' mastery of those outcomes. By clearly articulating the required competencies for a particular profession or field, educators can align their teaching methods and assessments to help students develop the necessary skills and knowledge.
- **Practical Training and Internships:** Providing students with opportunities for practical training and internships in relevant professional settings enhances their understanding of real-world contexts and develops their practical skills. These experiences bridge the gap between theory and practice, allowing students to apply their knowledge and acquire industry-specific competencies.
- **Collaborative Learning:** Collaborative learning environments, such as group projects and teamwork, promote effective communication, interpersonal skills, and cooperation among students. These skills are essential for professional competence, as many professions require individuals to work effectively in teams and collaborate with colleagues.
- **Guidance and Mentoring:** Effective guidance and mentoring by experienced professionals in the field can significantly contribute to the development of students' professional competence. Mentors can provide valuable insights, advice, and support, helping students navigate their educational journey and gain a deeper understanding of their chosen profession.
- **Continuous Assessment and Feedback:** Regular assessment and timely feedback are vital for students to monitor their progress and identify areas for improvement. Constructive feedback from educators and mentors helps students enhance their professional competence by highlighting their strengths and addressing any weaknesses.

- Technology Integration: Integrating relevant technologies into the learning process can enhance students' digital literacy and familiarize them with industry-specific tools and practices. Technological advancements in various fields have transformed professional practices, and equipping students with technological skills prepares them for future professional roles.
- Professional Ethics and Values: Emphasizing professional ethics, integrity, and values throughout the educational journey helps students develop a strong moral compass. Professional competence is not only about technical skills but also about ethical decision-making and responsible behavior in their chosen field.
- Lifelong Learning: Encouraging a mindset of lifelong learning is essential for the development of professional competence. Students should be motivated to stay updated with the latest advancements, research, and trends in their field, fostering a commitment to continuous self-improvement and professional growth.

By considering these pedagogical factors and integrating them into the educational process, educators can enhance the development of professional competence in students, preparing them for successful careers in their chosen fields.

Conclusion. Actual assessments, such as Case Studies, simulations, or project-based assignments, are more closely related to actual work situations than traditional exams. These assessments help students develop professional skills and knowledge in Real-world conditions. Regular, timely, and constructive feedback is important to help students develop their professional skills. Feedback should be specific to educational goals and aimed at identifying areas of improvement.

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